

LINGUACULTURAL FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT OF COLOUR

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Abstract: This article explains the concept. This explains the study of color names as a concept. The descriptive method is used in the article. Phraseologisms and toponyms for the article are presented as example. At the end of the article, the importance of research is highlighted.

Keywords: Concept, anthropocentric linguistics, toponyms, phraseologisms, linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics

INTRODUCTION

The concept of "concept" in Russian linguistics was introduced into scientific discourse in the first quarter of the 20th century by philosopher S. Askoldov. According to S. Askoldov, representatives of different nations communicate through concepts, and therefore, the creation and perception of concepts is considered a two-way communicative process. Such a system existing in the linguistic space determines the uniqueness of the national picture of the world.[1] So, if the concept of "concept" appeared in Russian linguistics in the 20th century, when did it appear in Uzbek linguistics and what purpose does it serve? Concept is a unit of anthropocentric linguistics, which we can encounter in linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics, and psycholinguistics. Among Uzbek linguists, Professor Nizomiddin Mahmudov explains the concept of "concept" as follows: "In linguocultural studies, attention is focused on the problems of expressing the concept itself. When familiarizing with Internet materials, for example, one can see that it is extremely widespread among linguists in Russia. It is difficult to count the works in this area, and even in recent years, a very large part of candidate dissertations have been devoted to the linguocultural study of the concept." [2] Scholar Durdon Khudoyberganova, who has thoroughly studied the research on the concept, comes to the following conclusion: "Concept is a mental structure. Moreover, it is multi-layered and multifaceted, as evidenced by the fact that it is currently being described as an object of psychological, cognitive-semantic, and linguocultural studies. Therefore, we assess the classification of concepts into subjective, social, and linguocultural types as an approach to a single essence from different aspects." [3] Concluding from many scientific works, the concept can be translated as a notion, but this only illuminates one side of the word. We can say that concept is a phenomenon associated with culture. For example, which aspect of color names should we study for it to be a concept? We need to study color names in connection with our culture. Because concept is a cultural unit for each nation.

It is known that color names are called coloronyms in world linguistics, and they have always attracted the attention of scientists and have been studied in various directions: structural-semantic, etymological, historical. However, none of their aspects have been studied in Uzbek linguistics. This determines the relevance of our scientific work.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE RELATED TO THE TOPIC

In world linguistics, Sevinch Abbasgulu kizi Maharramova and Vafa Eldar kizi Maharramova have conducted research on "White" and "Black" colors in terminology" (based on Russian and Azerbaijani languages), while Sapiga Elena V., Repina Marina V., and Zhukova Svetlana V., teachers at Kuban State Medical University, Krasnodar, have researched "Color terms in modern linguistics. Semantic and semiotic aspects."

Humans perceive nature and the world around them in color, connecting it with subjective judgments about the state of things, creating new objects, giving them not only shape but also color. Color serves as a cultural constant for development, becomes subjectivized, and also expresses national-cultural values. Color designations are found in lexemes, phrases, and phraseological units.

Linguistic research on colors includes the following directions: cultural aspect, the connection of color with culture; psychological features of color, lexical-semantic features, etymology, and gradunomy should be studied

METHODOLOGY

In the process of studying the concept of color, the etymology of color names also requires separate research. This is because there are cases when the expression of a word and its external image do not correspond to each other. For example, green tea should actually be called green tea, but we call it blue tea. Or the term "turning blue" in relation to illness is not actually referring to the blue color.

In our opinion, it is not entirely accurate to say that a person's color turns green. This is also emphasized by the interpretation of this meaning in Russian explanatory dictionaries: regarding the color of a person's face and skin. The prosecutor appeared to me, and not just to me but to everyone, very pale, almost with a green face. F. M. Dostoevsky, "The Brothers Karamazov" [4] In medical terminology, there are also terms such as "cyanosis, acrocyanosis" in relation to the color of the human face. In these conditions, a person's skin ranges from grayish-blue to dark blue. Based on this, it can be said that the Russian phrase "зеленое лицо" (green face) does not refer to a green face, but to a pale, blanched, grayish, bluish state. Thus, the word green, when referring to facial color, denotes a slight change in a person's normal facial color when nervous.

While in Russian the word *zelyoniy* (green) is used for tea, in Uzbek the word *ko'k* (blue) is used. In this case, the nomination is undoubtedly related to the fact that the green color is expressed by the word blue. After all, the color of tea made from green leaves is not blue, but green. It can be noted that the concepts underlying the words "yashil" and "zeleniy" in the Uzbek and Russian languages are directly or indirectly related to the etymology of this word. For example, in Russian, the word "zeleniy" was initially used in relation to unripe grapes. As a result, the word "zelyoniy" is used in the Russian language in relation to raw, unripe fruits and vegetables: *zelyoniy pomidor* (green tomato). As a result of the transformation of this meaning into a figurative one, the sememe "inexperienced, naive" was also formed: *Ya ne zelyoniy yunets, ya ne vchera na svet rodilsya* (I'm not a green youth, I wasn't born yesterday).

Such a concept exists in the Uzbek language. But it is not associated with color. Rather, it is expressed by the word "g'o'r" (naive): Malicious forces are inciting naive, inexperienced children against their parents and homeland, endangering their lives.

RESULTS

Color names exist in every language, and their expression is connected with the culture of the people. In order for us to take color names as a concept, we can cite their symbolic meanings. For example, white is a symbol of purity and goodness, black is a symbol of evil and mourning, and red is a symbol of love. Colors used in literary texts can serve as proof of our point:

1. On the tray were four flatbreads, two red chillaki grapes, and some kind of white grape pecked by a bird. (Oybek, Selected Works)
2. Shirinzabonov's face flushed red. "Mushtum."
3. This evening was a dark night that had taken into its black embrace the life and death matters of Otabek and Homid. (A. Qodiriy, Bygone Days.)

4. So, one side of my face is as bright as day, and the other side is as black as night. (X. To‘xtaboev, The Land of Sweet Melons.)

5. That's why people are getting used to the stories of the "yellow press" chasing events on the streets. From the newspaper

The occurrence of color names in place names is also connected with our national culture and the worldview of our people. For example, place names such as Oqdaryo, Qoradaryo, Qoraqush, Oqtapa, Qorabura, Qoraqulonchi, Qiziltepa are related to colors.

Color names also occur in phraseological units. For example: yuziga qizillik yugurmoq (to blush), qorasini ko‘rsatmaslik (to not show one's face), baxti qora bo‘lmoq (to be unlucky), ko‘ngli oq (to be pure-hearted).

In the following poem, the names of colors have a symbolic meaning:

I expected green love from you, Farewell now, my yellow leaf!

When I die, bring me not yellow flowers, But red ones.

In the poem, the names of colors represent the symbol of life.

DISCUSSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the study of color names as a concept reveals all aspects of our national colors related to culture and can be studied as a linguocultural unit. The fact that the study of color names is a separate object of research called coloronyms in world linguistics also requires the study of color names as a separate object of research in Uzbek linguistics. Such study should be beneficial not only for linguists but also for artists and painters. Because in these areas too, the expression of psychological and symbolic features of color names is of particular importance.

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